

The information needs of relatives of childhood cancer patients and survivors: A systematic review of qualitative evidence

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: To synthesize qualitative research on the information needs of relatives of childhood cancer patients and survivors.

Methods: Systematic searches of PubMed, PsycINFO, CINAHL, and Scopus identified relevant literature. Extracted data were combined using thematic synthesis. Methodological quality was assessed using the JBI critical appraisal tool for qualitative research.

Results: The review included 27 publications, with most research focusing on parents or primary caregivers. Five areas of information needs were identified: treatment, medication, and care; general information about cancer; coping and support; follow-up, late effects, and rehabilitation; and parenting and everyday life. Appropriateness of information depended on health care professionals' aptitude, message characteristics, communication setting, and relatives' personal factors. Preferences for form, sources, and timing for information provision varied.

Conclusion: The review identified information needs, communication barriers, and preferences among caregivers and siblings of childhood cancer patients and survivors, highlighting areas requiring further research and clinical consideration in addressing the identified challenges.

Practice implications: Caregivers and siblings have unique but similar information needs regarding childhood cancer. To ensure that these needs are met, health care professionals could use eHealth and mHealth technologies, assess each family member's knowledge, and create a safe and supportive environment for questions and feedback.

1. Introduction

A cancer diagnosis in children is rare, and families rarely have any information or experience. Every year about 225'000 children are newly diagnosed worldwide [1], and many families are profoundly affected by the disease. A childhood cancer diagnosis disrupts family functioning [2, 3] and can mobilize a support system where people other than immediate family members get involved in the care of the affected child [4]. During this delicate period, parents' responsibilities escalate as they are responsible for decision-making and assume a central role in caring for their child. Furthermore, they strive to preserve everyday family life and be involved in the daily care of their other children [5]. Grandparents

might help their children with material, practical and emotional support to help preserve optimal family functioning [6]. Siblings are also profoundly affected by the disease and are often closely involved in their sibling's care [7]. In addition to the organizational changes caused by the disease, childhood cancer challenges the emotional well-being of the affected families. Especially in the first months after the diagnosis, anxiety, and feelings of uncertainty and fear for the outcomes of the affected child are common among parents [8,9], siblings [10], and grandparents [11]. Those feelings might persist after treatment completion [3,12], as childhood cancer survivors are at an increased risk for cancer recurrence, secondary cancers, and other severe late effects.

Obtaining information may allow for dealing with uncertainty and

Abbreviations: ALL, Acute lymphoblastic leukemia; AML, Acute myeloid leukemia; APL, Acute promyelocytic leukemia; CML, Chronic myeloid leukemia; CNS, Central nervous system; eHealth, Electronic health; HCPs, Health care professionals; mHealth, Mobile health.

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coping with disease [13,14]. In cancer care, providing adequate information to patients has been associated with a lower level of psychological distress throughout the disease and better coping with the illness and its consequences [15]. However, information needs have been reported as the most prevalent among the unmet needs of parents of children with cancer at diagnosis and during treatment [16]. Information needs were also common among parents of survivors, who still desired more information, especially on late effects and follow-up care [17]. Ormandy [18] describes a patient health information need as “[...] a recognition that your knowledge is inadequate to satisfy a goal that you have, within the context/situation that you find yourself at a specific point in the time” (p. 99). In line with this definition, four dimensions are central to the understanding of patient information needs [18]: 1) the purpose the patient has for obtaining information (e.g., take a decision); 2) the specific context in which the person is located (e.g., sociodemographic characteristics); 3) the situation that prompted the need (e.g., a disease diagnosis); and 4) the specific timepoint at which the need arises. For this systematic review, Ormandy’s definition of patients’ information needs [18] will be used to understand relatives’ information needs, as a specific definition for the latter group is not yet available.

The information needs of relatives of adult cancer patients have been summarized in a systematic literature review [19]. Nevertheless, this study did not include relatives of children diagnosed with cancer and relatives of adult childhood cancer survivors. Considering the necessity to understand information needs from the perspective of the involved individuals and in light of their specific circumstances, the current review will focus on qualitative research, which allows for a more comprehensive and in-depth exploration of the context and meaning of participants’ experiences [20]. We aimed to summarize and describe qualitative research on: 1) the self-reported (unmet) information needs of relatives of children who were diagnosed with cancer; 2) their perceived barriers and facilitators to appropriate information acquisition; and 3) their preferences for information provision.

2. Methods

2.1. Protocol and registration

The current review is organized according to the PRISMA statement [21], and its protocol has been registered on the PROSPERO database (Registration number: CRD42022347283).

2.2. Search strategy

We systematically searched peer-reviewed research concerning the information needs of relatives of childhood cancer patients and survivors published until July 25, 2019, in PubMed, PsycINFO, CINAHL, and Scopus. A search update applying the same criteria was conducted on July 19, 2022. Four blocks with several free and thesaurus terms on “childhood”, “cancer”, “family members” and “information needs” were designed for each database (Appendix A). All the databases were searched using their default settings, but to reduce the number of irrelevant results, the “humans” filter was selected when possible. Additionally, a citation search of the reference lists of the included publications was conducted to identify any missed research.

2.3. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Studies were eligible if they applied qualitative methods to assess relatives’ self-reported information needs related to childhood cancer. Qualitative results from studies applying mixed methods were included if they reported results separately for quantitative and qualitative analyses. To include only the research referring to the contemporary and relevant information setting, studies were excluded where: 1) the focus was not on self-reported information needs of relatives of children who

received a childhood cancer diagnosis according to the International Classification of Childhood Cancer, third edition (ICCC-3) [22] (also excluding studies where children were older than 18 at diagnosis or diagnosed with other diseases, the focus was on other aspects or needs than information, on patients’ or survivors’ own information needs, or not self-reported needs of relatives); 2) only quantitative methods were used to assess and/or analyze information needs; 3) duplicate records; 4) publication was before 2007; 5) the report used languages other than English, German, French, Italian, Spanish, Dutch, Serbo-Croatian, and Romanian; and 6) other reasons (not an empirical research article, information needs assessment was not among the aims of the study, other reviews). Publications applying only quantitative methods and quantitative results of studies applying mixed methods for the analysis of relatives’ information needs will be synthesized in an upcoming separate review.

2.4. Selection of studies and data extraction

All the references identified through the database searches were imported into an EndNote X9 (first search) or EndNote 20 (second search) library, and duplicates were excluded using the automatic function of the software. The references were then imported in an Excel file (first search) or into the Rayyan [23] online software for systematic reviews (second search). Two reviewers (AI and KR, GM, or YS) independently screened titles and abstracts of all potentially relevant publications applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria described in Section 2.3. All the articles that were included by at least one reviewer were subjected to full-text screening. The same two reviewers completed full-text screening applying the same exclusion criteria. Discordance about inclusion was solved through discussion until consensus was reached or by involving a third reviewer.

Descriptive data about the included publications were extracted in an Excel table by the first author (AI) and validated by a second author (GM, KR, or YS). We extracted descriptive data about the study (author (s), title, year, country/countries of data collection, study design, method of data analysis, time point(s) of data collection), the population of interest (kinship or relationship with patient/survivor, sample size, gender) and childhood cancer patients/survivors (sample size, diagnosis). Qualitative results about the outcomes addressed in the current review were coded by the first author (AI). To ensure consistency in the coding and interpretation of data, a second author (YS) independently coded a random sample of 20% of the included publications (n = 6). The two authors discussed the assigned codes and agreed on the coding strategy to be applied to the remaining articles. When the included publications comprised information on individuals other than relatives and extended family members, these were not extracted to keep the current review’s focus on relatives’ personal and self-reported information needs and preferences. Extracted information included participants’ direct quotations and authors’ interpretations of results that were labeled as “results” or “findings” in the original article [24]. Data extraction was facilitated by using the ATLAS.ti 22 software for qualitative research. Two reviewers (AI and YS) independently appraised the methodological quality of all included publications. Interrater reliability was assessed using Cohen’s Kappa, and discordances about scoring criteria were solved through discussion until consensus was reached.

2.5. Quality assessment

The publications’ methodological quality was assessed using the Joanna Briggs Institute JBI Critical appraisal checklist for qualitative research [25], which was described as a coherent instrument to evaluate the validity of qualitative research [26]. The checklist consists of ten items that assess bias in study design, conduct, and analysis. Each item can be evaluated as “yes”, “no”, “unclear” or “not applicable”. The quality appraisal has been used to assess the overall strength of the results. None of the included publications were excluded from the current

review because of their methodological quality.

2.6. Data synthesis

Qualitative data on relatives' information needs have been integrated by the first author (AI) using thematic synthesis [24]. Thematic synthesis is a transparent and systematic method for synthesizing qualitative evidence recommended by Cochrane [27]. The synthesis method comprises three separate stages: 1) free "line-by-line" coding of primary authors' statements and participants' quotes in the result section of the included publications; 2) the grouping of similar "free codes" and the development of data-driven "descriptive themes"; and 3) the interpretation of primary research findings through the development of theory-driven "analytical themes" which include interpretations, explanations, and hypotheses formulated by the review authors [24]. Detailed subgroup analyses were conducted based on the timing of information needs along the cancer continuum (grouped as: diagnosis and active treatment; survivorship; multiple stages), the relationship between relatives and the child with cancer (grouped as: parents/primary caregivers; siblings; mixed kinship), and the World Bank classification of Gross National Income [28] of the country/countries of data collection (grouped as: high-income; upper-middle-income; lower-middle-income; or mixed-income levels). Data synthesis was facilitated by using the ATLAS.ti 22 software for qualitative research.

3. Results

The search identified 5190 records, of which 572 were automatically recognized as duplicates, and 4618 were subjected to title and abstract screening. After title and abstract screening, 184 potentially relevant publications were eligible for full-text screening. One additional publication was identified using citation searching of the reference lists of the included publications that were retrieved through the database searches. The current review included 27 articles reporting the results of

27 studies. For further details on the inclusion process, see Fig. 1.

3.1. Characteristics of included studies

Most included studies applied qualitative methods only (n = 21), and six used mixed methods. Most included studies (n = 20) were conducted in high-income countries, five in upper-middle-income countries, and two in lower-middle-income countries. Two studies included multiple data-collection countries, one of which included two high-income countries, and the other included four countries with different income levels. Participants were mainly parents and other primary caregivers (e.g., grandparents, aunts, adult siblings) whose role was similar to that of parents (n = 24). Hereafter, the term "caregivers" will refer to this group. Two studies addressed siblings' information needs specifically, and one included the perspectives of both parents and siblings. We did not identify any study describing the experiences of grandparents. The majority of included studies focused on information needs during the period of diagnosis and active treatment (n = 17) or survivorship (n = 6), and four studies addressed multiple stages along the cancer continuum, of which one also included bereavement. Most of the publications assessed general information needs (n = 15), but some studies investigated the information needs relating to: late effects, follow-up, and survivorship issues (n = 5); a specific cancer diagnosis (n = 3); specific treatments, care, and their side-effects (n = 3), and genetic testing (n = 1). A minority of the publications addressed specifically unmet information needs [38,42,46,48,50,51,53–55], and only three studies defined information needs [39,43,47]. Detailed characteristics for each included publication are presented in Table 1.

3.2. Data synthesis

Our analysis identified 189 free codes, organized into 22 descriptive themes, encompassing five analytical themes. Further details about the studies reporting different themes and direct quotations (Q) from the

Fig. 1. Overview of the selection process (PRISMA 2020).

Table 1
Characteristics of the included studies.

Frist author, year Country/countries of data collection (World Bank classification)	Title	Area of assessed information needs ^a Timing of information needs along the cancer continuum ^b	Methodology Assessment tool ^c Analysis method ^d	Participants	Childhood cancer diagnoses
Aburn, 2014 [29] New Zealand (High-income)	Education given to parents of children newly diagnosed with acute lymphoblastic leukemia: The parent's perspective	Acute lymphoblastic leukemia Diagnosis and active treatment	Qualitative Semi-structured interviews (n = 12) Grounded theory	Parents: n = 12 Mothers: n = 9	ALL: n = 12
Ahmadnia, 2021 [30] Iran (Lower-middle-income)	Survivor and parent engagement in childhood cancer treatment in Iran	Not specified Active treatment	Qualitative Interviews (n = 4) and focus groups (n = 1; n = 5 parents) Content analysis	Parents: n = 9/10* Mothers: n = 6/7* The study also included survivors (n = 19/20*)	Not reported
Cheng, 2009 [31] Hong Kong (High-income)	Oral mucositis: A phenomenological study of pediatric patients' and their parents' perspectives and experiences	Chemotherapy-induced oral mucositis Active treatment	Qualitative Semi-structured interviews (n = 22) Inductive content analysis	Parents: n = 22 Mothers: n = 20 Fathers: n = 1 Grandmother: n = 1 The study also included patients (n = 22)	ALL: n = 9 Lymphoma: n = 4 Osteosarcoma: n = 7 Others: n = 2
Doulavince Amador, 2018 [32] Brazil (Upper-middle-income)	The strength of information on retinoblastoma for the family of the child	Retinoblastoma Diagnosis and active treatment (outpatient)	Qualitative Semi-structured interviews (n = 10) Qualitative content analysis	Families: n = 10 Mothers: n = 9 Grandmothers: n = 1	Retinoblastoma Unilateral: n = 5 Bilateral: n = 5
Greenzang, 2018 [33] USA (High-income)	Parent perspectives on information about late effects of childhood cancer treatment and their role in initial treatment decision making	Late effects Active treatment	Qualitative Semi-structured interviews (n = 12) Thematic analysis	Parents: n = 12 Female: n = 9	Hematologic malignancy: n = 5 Brain tumor: n = 2 Extracranial solid tumor: n = 5
Hobbie, 2010 [34] USA (High-income)	Identifying the educational needs of parents at the completion of their child's cancer therapy	Not specified Treatment completion and early survivorship	Mixed methods Focus groups (n = 2/3*; n = 10 families) The study also included questionnaires (n = 15) Content analysis	Parents: n = 10 Mothers: n = 7 Fathers: n = 3	ALL AML Hodgkin disease Ewing sarcoma Brain tumor Osteosarcoma Brain tumor
Jackson, 2007 [35] Australia (High-income)	Pediatric brain tumor patients: Their parents' perceptions of the hospital experience	Brain tumors Diagnosis and active treatment	Qualitative Open-ended answers to interview question "How has your experience with the hospital been so far?" at four timepoints (T): T1: diagnosis T2: 6 months after diagnosis T3: 1 year after diagnosis T4: 2 years after diagnosis Thematic analysis	Parents: n = 73 T1: n = 53 T2: n = 41 T3: n = 38 T4: n = 45	Brain tumor
Kästel, 2011 [36] Sweden (High-income)	Parents' views on information in childhood cancer care	Not specified Diagnosis and active treatment	Qualitative Interviews at 5 timepoints during the first year after the diagnosis (n = 40) Content analysis	Relatives: n = 8 Participants changed at each timepoint but included mothers, fathers, or siblings (in substitution of parents) Parents: n = 10	Leukemia Solid tumors
Keats, 2019 [37] Canada (High-income)	After childhood cancer: A qualitative study of family physician, parent/guardian, and survivor information needs and perspectives on long-term follow-up and survivorship care plans	Long-term follow-up and survivorship care plans Survivorship	Qualitative Semi-structured interviews (n = 10) Deductive/inductive content analysis*	The study also included survivors (n = 8) and family physicians (n = 6)	ALL: n = 5 Osteosarcoma: n = 1 Lymphoma: n = 1 Nephroblastoma: n = 1 Germinoma: n = 1 Embryonal rhabdomyosarcoma: n = 1
Kelly, 2018 [38] USA (High-income)	The why behind the questions: Question-asking in parents of children newly diagnosed with cancer - A report from the Children's Oncology Group	Not specified Diagnosis and active treatment	Qualitative Interviews (n = 20) Constant comparative analysis	Parents: n = 20 Mothers: n = 16 Fathers: n = 4	Leukemia: n = 12 Rhabdomyosarcoma: n = 3 Osteosarcoma: n = 2 Ewing sarcoma: n = 1 Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma: n = 1 Wilms' tumor: n = 1

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Table 1 (continued)

Frist author, year Country/countries of data collection (World Bank classification)	Title	Area of assessed information needs ^a Timing of information needs along the cancer continuum ^b	Methodology Assessment tool ^c Analysis method ^d	Participants	Childhood cancer diagnoses
Kerr, 2007 [39] Canada (High-income)	Understanding the supportive care needs of parents of children with cancer: An approach to local needs assessment	Not specified Diagnosis and active treatment	Mixed methods Semi-structured interviews (n = 3) The study also included surveys (n = 15) Content analysis	Parents: n = 3 Mothers: n = 3	No information on the children of the n = 3 interviewed mothers
Kilicarslan-Toruner, 2013 [40] Turkey (Upper-middle-income)	Information-seeking behaviours and decision-making process of parents of children with cancer	Not specified Diagnosis and active treatment	Qualitative Semi-structured interviews (n = 15) Inductive content analysis	Parents: n = 15 Mothers: n = 13 Fathers: n = 2	ALL: n = 6 Neuroblastoma: n = 4 Wilms' tumor: n = 2 Non-Hodgkin lymphoma: n = 1 CML: n = 1 Rhabdomyosarcoma: n = 1 Not reported
Lövgren, 2016 [41] Sweden (High-income)	Bereaved siblings' advice to health care professionals working with children with cancer and their families	Not specified Multiple stages, including end-of-life care and bereavement	Qualitative Open-ended answers (n = 108) survey question "What advice would you give to HCPs working with children with cancer and their siblings?" Content analysis	Siblings: n = 108 Female: n = 69 Male: n = 39	Not reported
Lyu, 2019 [42] China (Upper-middle-income)	Unmet family needs concerning healthcare services in the setting of childhood hospitalization for cancer treatment in Mainland China: A qualitative study	Not specified Active treatment (hospitalization)	Qualitative Semi-structured interviews (n = 19) Inductive content analysis	Parents: n = 19 Mothers: n = 14 Fathers: n = 5	ALL: n = 16 Malignant lymphoma: n = 1 Neuroblastoma: n = 1 Malignant rhabdomyoma: n = 1
Maree, 2016 [43] South Africa (Upper-middle-income)	The information needs of South African parents of children with cancer	Not specified Active treatment	Qualitative Interviews (n = 13) and one follow-up interview (for purpose of clarification) Inductive thematic analysis	Parents: n = 12/13* Mothers: n = 8 Fathers: n = 2 Grandmother: n = 1 Aunt: n = 1	Leukemia: n = 7 Kidney cancer: n = 4 Optic nerve glioma: n = 1
Masika, 2020 [44] Tanzania (Lower-middle-income)	Concerns and needs of support among guardians of children on cancer treatment in Dar es Salaam: A qualitative study	Not specified Diagnosis and active treatment	Qualitative Focus groups (n = 3; n = 22 guardians) Thematic content analysis	Guardians (parents, grandparents, uncles and aunts, other persons who live and provide care for the child): n = 22 Female: n = 15 Male: n = 7	Leukemia: n = 5 Eye cancer: n = 5 Cancer of the glands: n = 5 Kidney cancer: n = 2 Stomach cancer: n = 1 Thyroid cancer: n = 1 Liver cancer: n = 1 Not reported
McCann, 2019 [45] El Salvador (Lower-middle-income), Guatemala (Upper-middle-income), Mexico (Upper-middle-income) and Panama (High-income)	Identifying and prioritizing family education needs at pediatric oncology centers in Central America and Mexico	Not specified Diagnosis and active treatment	Qualitative Semi-structured interviews (n = 71, including all participants) and focus groups (n = 4, including all participants). Separate data for families only were not available. Thematic analysis	Families (mothers, fathers, adult siblings, grandparents): n = 28 The study also included HCPs (n = 52) and communication professionals (n = 11)	Not reported
Patterson, 2011 [46] Australia (High-income)	The development of an instrument to assess the unmet needs of young people who have a sibling with cancer: Piloting the Sibling Cancer Needs Instrument (SCNI)	Not specified Multiple stages	Mixed methods Focus group (n = 1; n = 4 siblings) and telephone interviews (n = 7) The study also included a staff survey (n = 26) and a survey with siblings (n = 71) Thematic analysis and triangulation	Siblings: n = 11 Female: n = 5 The study also included staff (n = 26)	Bone/muscle: n = 4 Brain: n = 3 Lymphoma: n = 1 Leukemia: n = 1 Hodgkin's: n = 1 Non-Hodgkin's: n = 1
Ringnér, 2011 [47] Sweden (High-income)	Parental experiences of information within pediatric oncology	Not specified Multiple stages	Qualitative Focus groups (n = 4; n = 14 parents) and individual interviews	Parents of n = 11 children: n = 14 Mothers: n = 10 Fathers: n = 4	Leukemia: n = 5 Brain tumor: n = 2 Solid tumor: n = 4

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Table 1 (continued)

Frist author, year Country/countries of data collection (World Bank classification)	Title	Area of assessed information needs ^a Timing of information needs along the cancer continuum ^b	Methodology Assessment tool ^c Analysis method ^d	Participants	Childhood cancer diagnoses
Rodgers, 2016 [48] USA (High-income)	Processing information after a child's cancer diagnosis - how parents learn: A report from the Children's Oncology Group	Not specified Diagnosis and active treatment	(n = 4) Qualitative content analysis Qualitative Semi-structured interviews (n = 20) Constant comparative analysis	Parents: n = 20 Mothers: n = 16 Fathers: n = 4"	ALL: n = 10 AML: n = 1 APL: n = 1 Non-Hodgkin lymphoma: n = 1 Rhabdomyosarcoma: n = 3 Osteosarcoma: n = 2 Ewing sarcoma: n = 1 Wilms' tumor: n = 1 No information on the children of the n = 7 interviewed parents
Schaefer, 2022 [49] USA (High-income)	"Giving the gift of life twice": Understanding the lived experiences of parent donors and nondonors in pediatric haploidentical hematopoietic cell transplantation	Hematopoietic cell transplantation Active treatment (donation and transplant)	Qualitative Interviews (n = 7; with the purpose to inform the development of the questionnaire) and questionnaires with open-ended questions (n = 136) Framework method	Parents: n = 136 Mothers: n = 88 Fathers: n = 44 Other: n = 4 No information on the n = 7 interviewed parents	CNS tumor: n = 15
Schuele, 2019 [50] USA (High-income)	Information needs regarding cognitive late effects of caregivers of central nervous system tumor survivors	Cognitive late effects Survivorship	Qualitative Semi-structured interviews (n = 15) The study also included interviews with HCPs (n = 8) Grounded theory	Families/caregivers: n = 15 Female: n = 14 Male: n = 1 The study also included HCPs (n = 8)	Not reported: n = 22
Stub, 2021 [51] Norway (High-income)	Communication and information needs about complementary and alternative medicine: A qualitative study of parents of children with cancer	Complementary and alternative medicine Active treatment	Qualitative Semi-structured interviews (n = 22) Not specified	Parents of n = 22 children: n = 24 Female: n = 20 Male: n = 4	ALL: n = 3 AML: n = 2 Osteosarcoma: n = 2 Pontine glioma: n = 2 Hepatoblastoma: n = 1 Neuroblastoma: n = 1 Germ cell tumor: n = 1 Lymphoma: n = 1 No information specific to the children of the n = 31 interviewed parents
Tan, 2022 [52] Malaysia (Upper-middle-income)	Information needs of Malaysian parents of children with cancer: A qualitative study	Not specified Multiple stages	Qualitative Semi-structured interviews (n = 13) Thematic analysis using elements of Grounded theory	Parents of n = 13 children: n = 14 Mothers: n = 9 Fathers: n = 5 This study also included HCPs (n = 8)	ALL: n = 3 AML: n = 2 Osteosarcoma: n = 2 Pontine glioma: n = 2 Hepatoblastoma: n = 1 Neuroblastoma: n = 1 Germ cell tumor: n = 1 Lymphoma: n = 1 No information specific to the children of the n = 35 interviewed parents
Vetsch, 2017 [53] Australia (High-income)	"Forewarned and forearmed": Long-term childhood cancer survivors' and parents' information needs and implications for survivorship models of care	Late effects Survivorship	Mixed methods Semi-structured interviews (n = 31) This study also included self-administered questionnaires with parents (n = 163) and survivors (n = 322) Content analysis supplemented with the methodology described by Miles and Huberman (1994)	Parents: n = 31 A subsample of parents who responded to the questionnaire were interviewed. Separate data on interview participants were not provided. This study also included survivors (n = 39 were interviewed; n = 322 responded to the questionnaire)	No information specific to the children of the n = 35 interviewed parents
Vetsch, 2020 [54] Australia (High-income) and New Zealand (High-income)	Genetics-related service and information needs of childhood cancer survivors and parents: A mixed-methods study	Genetics Survivorship	Mixed methods Interviews (n = 35) This study also included questionnaires with parents (n = 218) and survivors (n = 404) Qualitative thematic analysis	Parents: n = 35 A subsample of parents who responded to the questionnaire were interviewed. Separate data on interview participants were not provided. This study also included survivors (n = 52 were interviewed; n = 404 responded to the questionnaire).	No information specific to the children of the n = 35 interviewed parents

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Table 1 (continued)

Frist author, year Country/countries of data collection (World Bank classification)	Title	Area of assessed information needs ^a Timing of information needs along the cancer continuum ^b	Methodology Assessment tool ^c Analysis method ^c	Participants	Childhood cancer diagnoses
Wakefield, 2012 [55] Australia (High-income)	Family information needs at childhood cancer treatment completion	Transition after treatment Early survivorship	Mixed methods Semi-structured telephone interviews assessing both quantitative and qualitative data Inductive coding applying the framework of Miles and Huberman (1994)	Parents: n = 78 Mothers: n = 44 Fathers: n = 34 Siblings: n = 15 This study also included survivors (n = 19)	No information specific to the children of the interviewed n = 78 parents and n = 15 siblings

Notes:

All information as stated in the original manuscript.

Abbreviations: ALL, Acute lymphoblastic leukemia; AML, Acute myeloid leukemia; APL, Acute promyelocytic leukemia; CML, Chronic myeloid leukemia; CNS, Central nervous system; HCPs, Health care professionals.

^a Some studies addressed information needs in a specific area, while other studies addressed information needs in general without restricting to a specific area.

^b Some studies assessed information needs retrospectively and the timing along the cancer continuum might not correspond to the children's disease stage at the time of the study.

^c Unless specified differently, this only refers to qualitative data assessed in the study.

* Inconsistent information throughout the manuscript

included studies are summarized in Table 2. In the results section, we indicated example quotes from Table 2 that support the claims.

3.2.1. Relatives' information needs

3.2.1.1. Treatment, medications and care. The majority of publications described relatives' information needs about treatment, medications and care. These needs were especially prominent in the studies addressing needs earlier along the cancer continuum, among caregivers and siblings, and studies conducted in high- and upper-middle-income countries. Specific areas included information about current treatment and different treatment options [30,32,35,37,39–44,46,48–50,52,55], their side effects (Q1) [31,35,38,40,42,44,46,48,52], alternative medicine [51], and information about caring for the child at home [29,31,33,34,36,38,40,42,45,48,51,52]. Caregivers described that this information helps them better prepare to support the child (Q2) and relieve their suffering (Q1).

3.2.1.2. General information about cancer. Another area where relatives reported high information needs concerns general information about cancer, such as causes [43–45,52,55], characteristics [29,30,32,35,39–44,46,48,50–52,55], and early symptoms of cancer [32,44,52], prognosis and survival chances [32,35,39–43,45,46,52], and risks of cancer development for other family members (Q3) [54,55]. This need was common among all relatives and along the entire cancer continuum. While participants from studies conducted in high- and upper-middle-income countries reported desiring disease-specific information about cancer, those from studies conducted in lower-middle-income countries reported desiring information about the causes of cancer, their responsibility (Q4), and mortality. For instance, caregivers recognized that their lack of education about cancer might influence their child's health outcomes and felt guilty for their child's disease. Similarly, siblings described the desire to get more information on what has caused their sibling's cancer, prognosis, recovery chances, and their own risk of developing the disease.

3.2.1.3. Coping and support. Participants further reported information needs concerning coping and support. Coping and support refer to information about practical [34,35,38,42,45,52,55] and emotional [38,40,45,46,48,51,52,55] support services available for families of children

with cancer (Q5). This information was especially reported by caregivers from studies conducted in high- and upper-middle-income countries and was important for them to better organize and cope with future challenges. Information needs about coping and support were reported along the entire cancer continuum. Many participants from studies conducted in upper-middle-income countries described the need for practical support as opposed to psychological support (Q6).

3.2.1.4. Follow-up, late effects and rehabilitation. Information about follow-up [37,48,52], rehabilitation after cancer care [46], and late effects [32–35,37,39,40,42,43,50,51,53,55] was common in the studies assessing information needs after cancer treatment completion, among caregivers, and studies conducted in high-income countries, but was not reported in studies conducted in lower-middle-income countries. Participants desired information about late effects in general [32,34,35,43,50], or specifically on mental and physical health [32,33,37,39,40,51,53], including fertility [53,55], surveillance plans and how to prevent and recognize a possible cancer recurrence [34,42,43], which was essential for them to prepare for future challenges (Q7 and Q8).

3.2.1.5. Parenting and everyday life. Participating caregivers mentioned having information needs about parenting children with cancer [34,40,42,43,49,52] and their siblings (Q9) [43,45] and everyday life changes (Q10) [37,38,45,48,51,52]. Information needs in this area were especially mentioned during treatment and in the studies conducted in high- and upper-middle-income countries.

3.2.2. Barriers and facilitators to appropriate information acquisition

3.2.2.1. Aptitude of HCPs. The aptitude of health care professionals (HCPs) was described as an important feature that might facilitate (Q11) or impede (Q12) appropriate information acquisition among relatives. HCPs' aptitude includes their availability to interact with relatives [29,30,32,35,36,38,40,42,47,48], encourage and answer their questions [29,36,38,40,47,48,54], provide accurate and clear explanations [29,30,35,36,38,41,42,47,48], repeat information [31,34,37–39,47,48], and personal traits such as patience [36,38,47,48], sensitivity [30,36,47,51], expertise [35], honesty [32,35,42,47], and empathy [30,31,35,36,40,47,48]. The aptitude of HCPs was mentioned as an important factor in all studies.

Table 2
Overview of descriptive and analytical themes.

Aim	Analytical themes	Descriptive themes	Example quotation	References
1	Information needs (area)	Treatment, medications and care	Quotation (Q)1: "I needed the doctor to explain to us what it's like to have OM [oral mucositis], the severity of it, and the extent of oral ulceration, how serious it was. It'd reassure me" (Parent, p. 834) [31] Q2: "I feel sad when my child does not want to eat. I do not know how to feed her, and I often need information about her nutrition." (Parent, p. 180) [40]	[29–46, 48–52,55]
		General information about cancer	Q3: "...[I don't know] if potentially future generations can have - like if my grandchildren are going to have yolk sac tumours." (Mother, p. 12) [54] Q4: "Did I do something wrong? I had never left my children without food, I always tried to keep our home clean." (Mother, p. 4) [45]	[29,30,32, 35,39–46, 48,50–52, 54,55]
	Coping and support		Q5: "Finally, one of the most important educational themes echoed by parents and the health care team was the emphasis on psychosocial education, from family support (including parents and siblings) to stress relief and relaxation." (Authors, p. 5) [45] Q6: "Information on how to obtain practical support needs are needed to assist parents in balancing these other responsibilities with caregiving for their sick child. This may include childcare for siblings, financial aid for medical and living costs, arrangements for leave from work, and temporary accommodations for those staying far from the treatment centers." (Authors, p. 146) [52]	[34,35,38, 40,42,45, 46,48,51, 52,55]
		Follow-up, late effects and rehabilitation	Q7: "I wanna know what's gonna happen... What are we really facing down the road? What is her life really gonna be like?" (Parent, p. 2) [33] Q8: "I think that information [about late effects] and knowledge is always useful; knowing when not to have to panic or being prepared	[32–35,37, 39,40,42, 43,46,48, 50–53,55]

Table 2 (continued)

Aim	Analytical themes	Descriptive themes	Example quotation	References
2	Barriers and facilitators	Parenting and everyday life	if something does happen. You can say, well yeah I knew that might have been a risk. You're sort of almost prepared for it – forewarned and forearmed." (Parent, p. 359) [53] Q9: "Furthermore, many of the children had siblings who also needed their parents to explain the situation concerning their brother or sister. Many parents wanted guidance on how to approach the topic." (Authors, p. 14) [43] Q10: "What am I supposed to do about work? How am I supposed to go to work when she can't go to daycare? You know, who is going to take care of her?" (Mother, p. 25) [38]	[34,37,38, 40,42,43, 45,48,49, 51,52]
		Aptitude of HCPs	Q11: "The experience and sensitive ear from the informant seems quite vital, including the capacity to read the families and to individualize the information." (Authors, p. 293) [36] Q12: "If we asked questions to the resident, then they would usually say that the information was in our folder and we should read about it. So, it kind of puts you off about asking questions to them" (Mother, p. 27) [38]	[29–32, 34–42,47, 48,51,54]
		Message	Q13: "The doctor should be transparent and clear in announcing the illness. We usually do not understand what doctors say [medical jargon]. A doctor should talk to us in simple words according to and based on our level of knowledge and understanding." (Parent, p. 5) [30] Q14: "Some parents also expressed that it would be helpful to understand how the combination of therapies impacted their child's likelihood of late effects, instead of learning separately about the late effects associated with each individual treatment or chemotherapeutic." (Authors, p. 3) [33] Q15: "Several also voiced wanting resources	[29,30, 32–43, 46–48, 50–55]

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Aim	Analytical themes	Descriptive themes	Example quotation	References
3	Preferred form of information	Setting	<p>to be available on an “as-needed” basis.” (Authors, p. 163) [50]</p> <p>Q16: “Some parents wanted time to connect with team members before they felt comfortable asking questions [...]” (Authors, p. 24) [38]</p> <p>Q17: “Siblings felt that information should be given [...] both with and without their parents being present.” (Authors, p. 300) [41]</p>	[30,35,36,38–41,47,48]
		Receiver’s personal factors	<p>Q18: “. . . it’s like the lady [physician] was saying it. but I couldn’t hear it.” (Parent, p. 456) [48]</p> <p>Q19: “We believed that we shouldn’t bother doctors and not to cause them headaches. My wife and I believed in and had faith in our doctor. We accepted whatever he told us because he had graduated and was an expert in this field so we trusted him” (Father, p. 4) [30]</p>	[29,30,35–40,45–48,50,51]
		Written (printed or online)	<p>Q20: “An online resource might be nice because then you could look whenever you happen to think that you don’t remember what the plan is. [...] I think that would take the anxiety level down a little bit.” (Caregiver, p. 163) [50]</p> <p>Q21: “Parents described having information available in their educational materials when questions arose as reassuring, “It kind of helped control some of that [uncertainty]” [...]” (Authors and mother, p. 25) [38]</p>	[29,30,33,36–40,43,47,48,50,51,54]
		Verbal	<p>Q22: “It would be great to talk to the person who is dealing exactly with your child’s problem” (Mother, p. 91) [32]</p> <p>Q23: “They also wanted scheduled follow-up information meetings with the physician, where they could sit down and look at the treatment schedule together, and regular contact with HCPs while the child was back at home.” (Authors, p. 248) [47]</p>	[29,32,39,47,54]
		Phone*	<p>Q24: “Sometimes there is not enough time at the outpatient department, and certain information</p>	[36]

Table 2 (continued)

Aim	Analytical themes	Descriptive themes	Example quotation	References
3	Preferred source of information	Activities and workshops	<p>has to be given by phone. This particular situation is very unsatisfactory to the families. The experience of being listened to and confirmed became most important. “Information by phone - how serious is this? We become more and more critical and observant.” [...]” (Authors and father, p. 292) [36]</p> <p>Q25: “Siblings also suggested that activities could be used while talking about difficult things, rather than just sitting down and talking.” (Authors, p. 300) [41]</p>	[41,47,54]
		Combination	<p>Q26: “Other parents felt a combination of written and spoken information was beneficial. One said: They gave us a booklet. I had gone through the booklet myself that you know to check you know certain things that I, that weren’t really making any sense. And I highlighted those things and when she (the professor) came around I asked her based on what I saw from the. (booklet).” (Authors and parent, p. 14) [43]</p>	[43,47,54]
		HCPs	<p>Q27: “The nurse often has an interpreting function, is often under less stress and can confront the physicians in order to get details.” (Authors, p. 293) [36]</p> <p>Q28: “The parents missed meeting a primary nurse and physician responsible for informing them, which contributed to their perceived need be on guard.” (Authors, p. 248) [47]</p>	[29,31,32,36,38,40,41,46–48,51,52]
		Integrated information system	<p>Q29: “They wanted the company of someone in the healthcare centre just to guide them step by step in every phase.” (Authors, p. 7) [30]</p>	[30]
		Societies and associations	<p>Q30: “[...] wished for controlled, scientific information about CAM [complementary and alternative medicine] preferably from the Children’s Cancer Society [...]” (Parents, p. 8) [51]</p>	[29,51]
		Other parents and internet**	<p>Q31: “Other families’ own experiences of caring for an ill child, their knowledge of how</p>	[29,30,38,40,47,52]

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Aim	Analytical themes	Descriptive themes	Example quotation	References
			to manage at home, and their real-world example were often more useful than the more sweeping, abstract descriptions obtained from the HCPs.” (Authors, p. 247) [47] Q32: “Additionally, parents sought information on their own if they felt that there was other information out there, “Well I asked questions and if I didn’t like what I had to hear I would Google it” [...]” (Authors and father, p. 25) [38]	
Preferred timing of information	Continuity		Q33: “Having good continuity of HCPs was also a part of feeling safe and secure.” (Authors, p. 247) [47] Q34: “Why in the world would you want to know- hear about the effects after you’ve already started or if you’re done. I’d wanna know... what we’re getting into before we get into it.” (Parent, p. 3) [33] Q35: “Most spoke about the need for information at the time of the diagnosis. One parent commented, “When my child was diagnosed it would have been best to sit down with someone and take some time and say okay, here was where it was located and here is the danger.” [...]” (Authors and parent, p. 288) [39]	[36,37,41, 43,47,48]
		Before treatment completion	Q36: “Although parents stated they needed information before or at the end of therapy about discerning symptoms, more specific risk factors (eg, late effects of therapy) may need to be delayed because of their desire to establish a new normal within their lives before dealing with late effects of therapy.” (Authors, p. 193) [34] Q37: “Statements made by the parents indicated that the need for information did not end after the child’s treatment had finished.” (Authors, p. 288) [39]	[30,33,34, 39,50,52]
	After treatment completion	Q38: “The parents emphasized that their needs for information did not decrease as time passed—on the contrary, after some time new and	[33,34,39, 47]	
		Critical periods		[47]

Table 2 (continued)

Aim	Analytical themes	Descriptive themes	Example quotation	References
			recurring questions left them needing more information. This was especially the case in later phases of the treatment, when the families sporadically visited the ward or the patient only got radiotherapy a few minutes each day.” (Authors, p. 248) [47]	

Notes:

Abbreviations: HCPs, Health care professionals; Q, Quotation.

* Reported as not preferred.

** Reported as preferred mainly when other more knowledgeable information sources are not available.

3.2.2.2. *Message.* Participants reported a preference for structured information [36–38,47,48,52] that is provided without the use of medical jargon (Q13) [29,30,36,38,41,42,48,53,55]. Despite the need for simple messages, they further recognized the need for reliable and precise [35, 37,40,42,43,47,48,50], research-based [51], and up-to-date [29] information. A further aspect that emerged, especially among participants from studies conducted in high-income countries, concerned the preference for individualized information, which is in line with relatives’ cultural values and native language [36,43], relevant to their specific situation (Q14) [29,33,34,36,37,50,51,55], and provided in the requested amount and when needed (Q15) [29,30,32,33,35,36,39,41, 47,48,50,53,54]. Siblings added that HCPs should consider that they might have different information needs than their parents [41] and need different explanations that are in line with their age [46] and the information provided to other family members [41].

3.2.2.3. *Setting.* A calm setting [47,48], establishing a good relationship with HCPs [30,35,36,38,40,47], and their physical presence [35, 36,38,40,47,48], facilitated building a relationship of trust and feeling comfortable with HCPs (Q16). The passage of time had a dual effect on caregivers. First, caregivers gained experience and became familiar with HCPs [38,40]. Conversely, it made new informational needs arise and increased difficulty persisting with questions [36,47]. Similarly, caregivers reported that the presence of other family members has a dual effect on appropriate information acquisition. They recognized that the presence of third parties reassures them that they will not miss any important piece of information [38,39]. However, other family members can also move the focus of the discussion to other aspects that are not directly relevant to caregivers [38]. Furthermore, caregivers have described their sick child’s presence as a limitation due to their desire to protect them from unpleasant information [39,47]. Similarly, siblings reported the desire to sometimes talk with HCPs without their parents being present (Q17) [41].

3.2.2.4. *Receiver’s personal factors.* A major theme that emerged among caregivers from studies conducted in high-income countries was their emotional burden shortly after the diagnosis [35,36,38,40,45,47,48, 51], when relatives recognized the inability to process any further information (Q18). They also mentioned that they receive most of the information at this time, and some caregivers reported feeling over-informed [29,35,36,38,48,50]. Participants, especially caregivers from studies conducted in high-income countries, reported that pre-existing knowledge affects further information acquisition [36,38, 48]. Some described not knowing enough to ask questions, but at the same time, they recognized that gaining knowledge helped them to ask more precise questions. Contrarily, the desire to avoid disagreement or

pressing HCPs with questions [30,36,47] were factors hindering question-asking (Q19) or were perceived to improve the quality of care received by the child. Positive feelings facilitating information acquisition included establishing a good relationship with HCPs that fostered reciprocity [35,47,48], feeling listened to and taken seriously [30,39,40,51], or being empowered and involved in important discussions [29,37,46].

3.2.3. Preferred form of information

The preferred form of information entails aspects of the channel used to deliver information. Studies conducted in lower-middle-income countries reported limited results on the preferred form of information among relatives.

3.2.3.1. Written (printed or online). Caregivers reported preferring receiving information in a written form, either paper-based (especially at diagnosis and active treatment) [29,30,33,36,39,43,47,48,51,54] or online (especially at survivorship; Q20) [37,50,51,54]. When information was available online, participants preferred online resources approved by their physicians [29,50,51]. Written resources allowed them to access the needed information at any time in specific situations [29,38,40] and helped them cope with emotional distress (Q21).

3.2.3.2. Verbal. Verbal information involves formal meetings with HCPs, which allow for remaining updated on the development of the disease and treatment, and clarifying any doubts (Q22 and Q23) [29,32,39,47,54]. Preferences for verbal information were reported mainly among caregivers. However, receiving information on the phone was not desirable among this group (Q24) [36].

3.2.3.3. Activities and workshops. Some participants reported that seminars and activities could be effective resources for getting information about cancer [41,47,54]. This preference was prevalent among siblings (Q25).

3.2.3.4. Combination. Some caregivers also mentioned a combination of different forms of information as the best way to obtain information (Q26) [43,47,54]. No studies reporting on siblings or from studies conducted in lower-middle-income countries have described this preference.

3.2.4. Preferred source of information

We have only found evidence on the preferred sources of information for other times than survivorship. Regarding the preferred sources of siblings, there was only limited evidence.

3.2.4.1. HCPs. The preferred sources participants mentioned were HCPs, mainly physicians and nurses (Q27 and Q28) [29,31,32,36,38,40,41,46–48,51,52]. Participants appreciated receiving information directly from the physician caring for the child but recognized this was often challenging because of time constraints. Therefore, they reported that nurses were essential in clarifying and directing their questions to the physician whenever they could not answer themselves (Q27).

3.2.4.2. Integrated information system. Among caregivers from studies conducted in lower-middle-income countries, some have also mentioned the need for an integrated information system and a reference person to guide them throughout the cancer journey (Q29) [30].

3.2.4.3. Societies and associations. A few studies conducted among caregivers from high-income countries mentioned external cancer societies or foundations as a valuable source of general information about cancer or complementary and alternative medicine at the time of cancer treatment (Q30) [29,51].

3.2.4.4. Other parents and internet. Some caregivers have mentioned other parents (Q31) [29,30,40,47,52] and self-identified internet web-pages (Q32) [30,38,40,47] as possible sources of information. They recognized the possibility of not receiving accurate information about their situation, but these two sources were helpful for participants when information was not provided by more knowledgeable sources. Other parents were also described as an important source for experience-based information, sometimes valued better than explanations provided by HCPs (Q31) [30,47,52].

3.2.5. Preferred timing of information

Participants, including especially caregivers, reported preferences for continuity (Q33) [36,37,41,43,47,48] in information provision along the entire cancer continuum, from diagnosis (Q34 and Q35) [30,33,34,39,50,52] to after treatment completion (Q36 and Q37) [33,34,39,47]. Some participants described these milestones as critical periods when they would have needed information but felt abandoned by HCPs (Q38) [47].

3.3. Quality appraisal

The results of the quality assessment are available in Table 3. The two reviewers agreed on 93% of the assigned scores, with Cohen's Kappa indicating substantial agreement ($k = 0.757$) [56]. The included publications showed an overall good methodological quality (mean number of "yes": 8.2; SD 1.2, range: 5–10).

4. Discussion and conclusion

4.1. Discussion

This review identified areas where relatives report diverse information needs, common barriers and facilitators to appropriate information acquisition, and preferences about form, source, and timing for information provision. Our results are based on a thematic synthesis of 27 publications reporting qualitative results of primary studies on relatives' information needs. Most publications focused exclusively on parents and other primary caregivers ($n = 24$) and high-income countries ($n = 20$). Only two studies addressed specifically siblings' information needs, and both were conducted in high-income countries. We have not identified any publication addressing grandparents' information needs or conducted in low-income countries. Five major information needs areas were: treatment, medication, and care; general information about cancer; coping and support; follow-up, late effects, and rehabilitation; and parenting and everyday life. We found that unmet information needs only occasionally are due to a lack of information provision from the HCPs. Instead, they result from a failure in the process of information acquisition. Our review showed that appropriate information acquisition is best reached when relatives perceive a favorable aptitude of HCPs, the message is simple, reliable, and tailored to their specific situation, the communication occurs in the desired setting, and when they feel to have established a satisfactory mutual relationship with HCPs. Relatives' self-reported preferences for information provision were described in terms of form, sources, and timing.

Caregivers mentioned a broad range of information needs, encompassing all five identified areas. Nevertheless, some differences were observed among caregivers from high- and upper-middle-income countries and caregivers from lower-middle-income countries. While caregivers from high- and upper-middle-income countries described information needs about their child's specific condition, caregivers from lower-middle-income countries reported desiring additional information, especially on the causes of the disease, their responsibility, and mortality risks. Information needs about coping and support, follow-up, late effects, and rehabilitation, and parenting and everyday life have mainly been observed among caregivers from high- and upper-middle-income countries. These differences may be due to the cultural and

Table 3

Results of the quality appraisal of included publications according to the JBI critical appraisal checklist for qualitative research.

First author, year	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	No. yes
Aburn, 2014 [29]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	8
Ahmadnia, 2021 [30]	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	No	Yes	6
Cheng, 2009 [31]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	9
Doulavince Amador, 2018 [32]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	8
Greenzang, 2018 [33]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	9
Hobbie, 2010 [34]	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	No	No	Yes	Yes	5
Jackson, 2007 [35]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	8
Kästel, 2011 [36]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	9
Keats, 2019 [37]	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	8
Kelly, 2018 [38]	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	8
Kerr, 2007 [39]	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	8
Kilicarslan-Toruner, 2013 [40]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	8
Lövgren, 2016 [41]	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	7
Lyu, 2019 [42]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	8
Maree, 2016 [43]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	9
Masika, 2020 [44]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	9
McCann, 2019 [45]	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	6
Patterson, 2011 [46]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Unclear	No	Yes	Yes	7
Ringné, 2011 [47]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	9
Rodgers, 2016 [48]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	9
Schaefer, 2022 [49]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	9
Schuele, 2019 [50]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	9
Stub, 2021 [51]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	9
Tan, 2022 [52]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	10						
Vetsch, 2017 [53]	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	9
Vetsch, 2020 [54]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	10						
Wakefield, 2012 [55]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	8

Notes:

- 1) Congruity between stated philosophical perspective and research methodology.
- 2) Congruity between research methodology and the research question or objectives.
- 3) Congruity between the research methodology and the methods used to collect data.
- 4) Congruity between the research methodology and the representation and analysis of data.
- 5) Congruity between the research methodology and the interpretation of results.
- 6) Is there a statement locating the researcher culturally or theoretically?
- 7) Is the influence of the researcher on the research, and vice-versa, addressed?
- 8) Are participants, and their voices, adequately represented?
- 9) Is the research ethical according to current criteria or, for recent studies, and is there evidence of ethical approval by an appropriate body?
- 10) Do the conclusions drawn in the research report flow from the analysis, or interpretation, of the data?

societal stigma associated with childhood cancer in some lower-middle-income countries and misconceptions about its causes and treatments [57]. Differences were also observed regarding barriers and facilitators to appropriate information acquisition among different country income levels. We found caregivers from high- and upper-middle-income countries to report receiving more information than they could process. This can lead to a situation where caregivers feel overwhelmed by the amount of information they have to process and interpret, especially at the initial stage of the disease when they also experience intense emotional distress [58]. Our results showed that in lower-middle-income countries, caregivers were likely to rely on HCPs for information and guidance and were intimidated by the prospect of asking questions or seeking clarifications [57]. Regulations and uses on information provision to the parents of children with cancer may vary by country, with stricter regulations applied in high-income countries. Additionally, in lower-middle-income countries, the healthcare system may be less developed, and caregivers may have limited access to medical information and resources. In these contexts, caregivers may be less likely to ask questions or seek additional information out of respect for HCPs, or fear of appearing distrustful or demanding [57]. Caregivers reported a preference for written and verbal information, or a combination of both, provided that the information was trustworthy and approved by their HCP.

Siblings mentioned information needs similar to those of caregivers. However, they further stressed desiring additional information on the causes of cancer, their own risk of developing the disease, and the prognosis for their sick sibling. The main barriers to appropriate information acquisition reported by siblings concerned: not being involved

enough in discussions about their sibling’s disease, not receiving consistent information to that provided to parents, receiving unclear or vague information, and having the opportunity to talk with HCPs only with the presence of their parents. Siblings may feel that their parents’ presence hinders their possibility to speak honestly and freely about their feelings. They might be concerned about being judged or criticized by their parents or not being completely understood. Another possible explanation may be that sharing their concerns in front of their parents could further upset the latter [59], who are already burdened with responsibilities and fears for the sick child. Siblings described preferences for information provided through activities and workshops. Some examples of activities and workshops that may be helpful for siblings of children with cancer include support groups, art or music therapy, educational sessions, and camps or recreational activities [60]. These activities can provide siblings with a safe and supportive setting to learn and connect with other children who are going through similar experiences. By participating in these activities and workshops, siblings could better understand childhood cancer, improve their coping skills, and feel more connected and supported during a challenging time [61–63].

4.1.1. Strengths and limitations

Our results should be interpreted considering some limitations. First, most of the included publications have addressed caregivers’ information needs and information needs of relatives in high-income countries, and our results mainly apply to these specific groups of relatives. Further research is needed to consider the voices of siblings, grandparents, and relatives in low-income countries. Second, there was heterogeneity among the studies, with possible differences in how information needs

were defined and assessed. Most of the included publications did not define information needs or formally distinguish between met and unmet information needs. Finally, we acknowledge that some studies did not differentiate between reported past experiences with information and actual needs and preferences about information provision.

To our knowledge, the current review is the first to provide a qualitative summary of the self-reported information needs of relatives of children with cancer. We searched four major scientific databases in medicine and psychology and screened over 5'000 publications. Our results are drawn from 27 primary studies that showed good methodological quality, strengthening our results. We have included research conducted in both high- and middle-income countries and research including diverse relatives, childhood cancer diagnoses, and time points along the cancer continuum.

5. Conclusion

Our review identified different areas where relatives reported having information needs along the cancer continuum, the aspects of communication that may impede proper information acquisition, and their preferred ways to receive information on childhood cancer. Despite the challenge of identifying and providing the correct form and amount of information at the right time to each family member, our review identified some aspects that should be further considered in clinical practice and future research.

5.1. Practice implications

Our review showed that caregivers and siblings have similar yet unique information needs and preferences. Given the effects of information on relatives' and patients' psychosocial outcomes [53,64,65], it is vital to find solutions that accommodate these needs. HCPs could initially assess each family member's knowledge, understanding, and information needs related to the child's cancer diagnosis and treatment. This can help identify which family members require more information and what topics to focus on. Since individualized and attentive communication with each family member might be challenging for

HCPs, additional instruments for information acquisition should be used. Electronic health (eHealth) and mobile health (mHealth) technologies allow information to be tailored to specific situations and enable users to have access to information upon request [66]. Such technologies might provide extensive opportunities for education and information on childhood cancer among relatives [67] and in countries with lower income levels [68]. Additionally, especially in lower-middle-income countries, HCPs should create a safe and supportive environment where relatives feel comfortable asking questions and providing feedback. This should help identify areas where further information or support is needed and can also help build trust with caregivers.

Ethical approval

Ethical approval was not required.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Anica Ilic: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing, Visualization, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Yara Sievers:** Validation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Katharina Roser:** Methodology, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Katrin Scheinemann:** Writing – review & editing. **Gisela Michel:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

None to declare.

Appendix A. Database search blocks

	PubMed	PsycINFO	CINAHL	Scopus
Block 1: Child	child OR child* OR kid* OR baby* OR infant OR infant* OR newborn* OR neonat* OR neonat* OR pediatric* OR paediatric* OR girl* OR boy* OR toddler* OR "pre-schooler" OR preschooler* OR "pre schooler" OR "pre schoolers" OR adolescent OR adolescen* OR young* OR youth* OR teen*	child* OR kid* OR baby* OR infant* OR newborn* OR neonat* OR pediatric* OR paediatric* OR girl* OR boy* OR toddler* OR "pre-schooler" OR preschooler* OR "pre schooler" OR "pre schoolers" OR adolescent health OR adolescen* OR young* OR youth* OR teen*	child OR child* OR kid* OR baby* OR infant OR infant* OR newborn* OR neonat* OR neonat* OR pediatric* OR paediatric* OR girl* OR boy* OR toddler* OR "pre-schooler" OR preschooler* OR "pre schooler" OR "pre schoolers" OR adolescent health OR adolescen* OR young* OR youth* OR teen*	child OR child* OR kid* OR baby* OR infant OR infant* OR newborn* OR neonat* OR neonat* OR pediatric* OR paediatric* OR girl* OR boy* OR toddler* OR {pre-schooler} OR preschooler* OR {pre schooler} OR {pre schoolers} OR adolescent OR adolescen* OR young* OR youth* OR teen*
Block 2: Kinship	grandparents OR grandparent* OR "grand parent" OR "grand parents" OR grandmother* OR "grand mother" OR "grand mothers" OR grandfather* OR "grand father" OR "grand fathers" OR grandchild* OR "grand child" OR "grand children" OR granddaughter* OR "grand daughter" OR "grand daughters" OR grandson* OR "grand son" OR "grand sons" OR parents OR parent* OR mother* OR father* OR daughter* OR son* OR siblings OR sibling* OR brother* OR sister* OR spouses OR spouse* OR partner* OR husband* OR wife* OR	grandparents OR grandparent* OR "grand parent" OR "grand parents" OR grandmother* OR "grand mother" OR "grand mothers" OR grandfather* OR "grand father" OR "grand fathers" OR grandchild* OR "grand child" OR "grand children" OR granddaughter* OR "grand daughter" OR "grand daughters" OR grandson* OR "grand son" OR "grand sons" OR parents OR parent* OR mother* OR father* OR daughter* OR son* OR siblings OR sibling* OR brother* OR sister* OR spouses OR spouse* OR partner* OR husband* OR wife* OR	grandparents OR grandparent* OR "grand parent" OR "grand parents" OR grandmother* OR "grand mother" OR "grand mothers" OR grandfather* OR "grand father" OR "grand fathers" OR grandchild* OR "grand child" OR "grand children" OR granddaughter* OR "grand daughter" OR "grand daughters" OR grandson* OR "grand son" OR "grand sons" OR parents OR parent* OR mother* OR father* OR daughter* OR son* OR siblings OR sibling* OR brother* OR sister* OR spouses OR spouse* OR partner* OR husband* OR wife* OR	grandparents OR grandparent* OR {grand parent} OR {grand parents} OR grandmother* OR {grand mother} OR {grand mothers} OR grandfather* OR {grand father} OR {grand fathers} OR grandchild* OR {grand child} OR {grand children} OR granddaughter* OR {grand daughter} OR {grand daughters} OR grandson* OR {grand son} OR {grand sons} OR parent OR parent* OR mother* OR father* OR daughter* OR son* OR siblings OR sibling* OR brother* OR sister* OR spouses OR spouse* OR partner* OR husband* OR wife* OR

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	PubMed	PsycINFO	CINAHL	Scopus
	wive* OR daughter* OR son* OR caregivers OR caregiver* OR carer* OR "care giver" OR "care givers" OR famil* OR relative* OR friends OR friend* OR "important other" OR "important others" OR "significant other" OR "significant others"	wive* OR daughter* OR son* OR caregivers OR caregiver* OR carer* OR "care giver" OR "care givers" OR famil* OR relative* OR friendship OR friend* OR "important other" OR "important others" OR "significant other" OR "significant others"	wive* OR daughter* OR son* OR caregivers OR caregiver* OR carer* OR "care giver" OR "care givers" OR famil* OR relative* OR friendship OR friend* OR "important other" OR "important others" OR "significant other" OR "significant others"	wive* OR daughter* OR son* OR caregivers OR caregiver* OR carer* OR "care giver" OR "care givers" OR famil* OR relative* OR friend OR friend* OR "important other" OR "important others" OR "significant other" OR "significant others"
Block 3: Information needs	Needs assessment OR "information need" OR "information needs" OR "need for information" OR "need of information" OR "health information" OR "information preference" OR "information preferences" OR "knowledge need" OR "knowledge needs" OR "wish for information" OR "wish of information" OR "desire for information" OR "desire of information" OR "request for information" OR "requests of information" OR "informational need" OR "informational needs" OR "informative need" OR "informative needs"	Needs assessment OR "information need" OR "information needs" OR "need for information" OR "need of information" OR "health information" OR "information preference" OR "information preferences" OR "knowledge need" OR "knowledge needs" OR "wish for information" OR "wish of information" OR "desire for information" OR "desire of information" OR "request for information" OR "requests of information" OR "informational need" OR "informational needs" OR "informative need" OR "informative needs"	Information needs OR "information need" OR "information needs" OR "need for information" OR "need of information" OR "health information" OR "information preference" OR "information preferences" OR "knowledge need" OR "knowledge needs" OR "wish for information" OR "wish of information" OR "desire for information" OR "desire of information" OR "request for information" OR "requests of information" OR "informational need" OR "informational needs" OR "informative need" OR "informative needs"	information demand OR {information need} OR {information needs} OR {need for information} OR {need of information} OR {health information} OR {information preference} OR {information preferences} OR {knowledge need} OR {knowledge needs} OR {wish for information} OR {wish of information} OR {desire for information} OR {desire of information} OR {request for information} OR {requests of information} OR {informational need} OR {informational needs} OR {informative need} OR {informative needs}
Block 4: Disease	neoplasms OR neoplasm* OR cancer* OR malign* OR tumor* OR tumour* OR oncolog* OR carcinoma* OR leukemia* OR leukaemia* OR lymphoma* OR medulloblastoma* OR sarcom* OR radiotherapy OR radiotherap* OR chemoradiotherapy OR chemotherapy , adjuvant OR induction chemotherapy OR consolidation chemotherapy OR maintenance chemotherapy OR chemotherapy* OR surgical oncology OR "surgical oncology" OR "curative surgery"	neoplasms OR neoplasm* OR cancer* OR malign* OR tumor* OR tumour* OR oncolog* OR carcinoma* OR leukemia* OR leukaemia* OR lymphoma* OR medulloblastoma* OR sarcom* OR radiotherapy OR radiotherap* OR chemotherapy OR chemotherap* OR "surgical oncology" OR "curative surgery"	neoplasms OR neoplasm* OR cancer* OR malign* OR tumor* OR tumour* OR oncolog* OR carcinoma* OR leukemia* OR leukaemia* OR lymphoma* OR medulloblastoma* OR sarcom* OR radiotherapy OR radiotherap* OR chemoradiotherapy OR chemotherapy , cancer OR chemotherap* OR "surgical oncology" OR "curative surgery"	neoplasms OR neoplasm* OR cancer* OR malign* OR tumor* OR tumour* OR oncolog* OR carcinoma* OR leukemia* OR leukaemia* OR lymphoma* OR medulloblastoma* OR sarcom* OR cancer radiotherapy OR radiotherap* OR chemoradiotherapy OR cancer chemotherapy OR cancer surgery OR {surgical oncology} OR {curative surgery}

Note: Thesaurus/MeSH terms are reported in bold

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